

Abstract

Characterisation of Fibromyalgia Types and the Seven Main Etiological Causes.

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Abstract

Fibromyalgia is a complex chronic syndrome characterised by widespread musculoskeletal pain, persistent fatigue, sleep disturbances, cognitive impairment, and a broad range of systemic symptoms. Despite its high prevalence, it continues to pose significant diagnostic and therapeutic challenges due to its multifactorial and heterogeneous nature. This paper aims to characterise the main types of fibromyalgia and identify seven fundamental etiological causes involved in its development, based on an integrative and functional clinical approach.

From a physiological and functional perspective, fibromyalgia can be classified into different types depending on the predominance of neurological, musculoskeletal, metabolic, immunological, endocrine, emotional, or chronic inflammatory/infectious dysfunctions. These categories are not mutually exclusive and frequently coexist, contributing to the clinical variability observed among patients.

The seven primary causes identified include chronic emotional stress, sleep disorders, autonomic nervous system dysfunction, hormonal imbalances, immune system alterations, metabolic toxicity, and the presence of persistent inflammatory or infectious processes. The dynamic interaction of these factors leads to alterations in pain perception, central sensitisation phenomena, and neurovegetative dysregulation, which are often undetected by conventional diagnostic methods.

The results presented reinforce the importance of an individualised diagnostic model that integrates structural and functional aspects, allowing for a deeper understanding of the pathophysiology of fibromyalgia. Identifying different clinical types and their respective etiological causes may contribute to more targeted and effective therapeutic strategies, promoting an integrated approach between conventional and complementary medicine.

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